

Enabling transition towards circular and systemic BIOeconomy model regions by a Regions-to-Regions approach

Report on final concept of BIO2REG network

Deliverable 2.1

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Glossary

BIOC: BIOCUM Interrelations

FZJ: BioökonomieREVIER, Forschungszentrum Jülich

KVC: Kveloce

MCA: Multi-Criteria Assessment

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1 Introduction

This document (Deliverable 2.2) contains both the final concept for the BIO2REG network, and the description of the systematic design process followed to reach this final concept. This process encompassed mapping of existing bioeconomy initiatives, iterative concept development, and validation through Advisory Forum consultations and regional stakeholder engagement, creating a platform that complements and enhances the current European bioeconomy landscape.

In recent years, numerous European projects have been actively working to develop tools and frameworks to promote bioeconomy development across various regions of Europe (Annex 1). These initiatives have taken diverse approaches to support the transition towards more sustainable, bio-based economies at the regional level.

Many projects focus on developing specialized tools, guides, and methodologies. For instance, [BIOMODEL4REGIONS](#) supports innovative regional governance models for better-informed decision-making and demonstrates results in pilot regions, while [SUSTRACK](#) has developed monitoring and assessment tools for tracking environmental, social and economic impacts of the transition from fossil-based to circular biobased systems. Other projects like [POWER4BIO](#) have focused on increasing the capacity of regional and local policy makers to structure their bioeconomy, offering knowledge exchange and best practice sharing.

Knowledge transfer represents another key focus area across several initiatives. [BE-Rural](#) has established Open Innovation Platforms in five Eastern European countries to facilitate knowledge-sharing between rural stakeholders and engage citizens through interactive formats. Similarly,

[BIOREGIO](#) has promoted circular economy of biological streams, improving knowledge and increasing recycling rates through policy development and stakeholder meetings. The [ROBIN](#) project is working on improving bioeconomy governance practices and enhancing understanding of bioeconomy benefits among all stakeholders.

Other crucial components found in some existing projects are the networking activities. The European Bioeconomy Network ([EuBioNet](#)) connects 160 EU-funded projects and initiatives focused on bioeconomy promotion, maximising knowledge sharing and identifying impact-oriented strategies. The [BIOEAST](#) Initiative has focused on developing cross-sectorial bioeconomy strategies for Central and Eastern Europe and establishing multi-stakeholder networks. Projects like [BioVoices](#) have created Mobilisation and Mutual Learning platforms to increase the quality, relevance and social acceptability of bio-based products, supporting co-creation among quadruple helix stakeholders.

Some initiatives have developed comprehensive service offerings. [MainstreamBio](#) provides a range of tools and resources to support small-scale bio-based solutions, including catalogues, best practices and educational materials. Similarly, [BioRural](#) offers a platform connecting rural bioeconomy initiatives through a publicly available toolkit that integrates knowledge sharing, networking capabilities and business model development.

Against this backdrop of existing bioeconomy support initiatives, the BIO2REG network has been conceptualized with careful consideration of the current landscape. The network's design aims to build upon existing foundations, complement current offerings, fill identified gaps, and create meaningful synergies with other projects and established platforms like [MainstreamBio](#) and [BioRural](#).

The BIO2REG network will differentiate itself through specialized stakeholder guides on transition measures and Multi-Criteria Assessment methodologies that bridge theoretical concepts with practical implementation steps. Its exchange instrument, featuring mentoring services and on-site visits for participants to observe relevant project developments and initiatives in other regions, will offer a deeper, more personalized learning experience than primarily digital platforms by facilitating direct experience exchange.

Additionally, BIO2REG will seek to extend and update training content from completed projects, filling the gaps in implementation guidance, and providing continuity for valuable resources developed by previous initiatives. By building upon existing foundations while adding new dimensions focused on transition implementation, BIO2REG ensures knowledge remains accessible and current for regions at all stages of bioeconomy development.

Through its resource's repository, community spaces, training services, thematic matchmaking events, and coordinated events calendar, BIO2REG provides holistic support for regions navigating the complex journey of bioeconomy transition while complementing and enhancing the valuable work already established in the European bioeconomy network landscape.

This document presents the conceptual framework and implementation strategy for the BIO2REG network, a comprehensive platform designed to support regional bioeconomy transition across Europe by connecting stakeholders, facilitating knowledge exchange, and providing tailored resources and services that complement and enhance existing bioeconomy initiatives.

2 Methodology for the Development of the Network Concept

The development of the BIO2REG network concept followed a systematic and evidence-based approach, consisting of three key phases: (1) a comprehensive mapping and analysis of existing bioeconomy initiatives, (2) the formulation of an initial network concept based on identified gaps and opportunities, and (3) a dual validation process involving both expert consultation and potential user feedback.

Figure 1. Network development methodology

2.1 Mapping of Bioeconomy Initiatives

The first step in developing the BIO2REG network concept involved a comprehensive mapping of existing bioeconomy projects and initiatives across Europe. This exercise aimed to understand the current landscape of bioeconomy support mechanisms, identify successful approaches, and pinpoint gaps or areas for improvement.

A structured analysis framework was applied to examine each initiative, with particular attention given to:

- Objectives, target audiences and stakeholders and types of services offered
- Development status: Starting, Ongoing, Mature, Completed – Operational, Completed – Non-operational, Renewed / New Phase
- Online presence and digital platforms

Special emphasis was placed on initiatives featuring online hubs or networking platforms similar to the envisioned BIO2REG network. These were analysed in greater detail to understand their functionality, user experience, and value proposition. The resulting table (Annex 1) provided a clear overview of the existing ecosystem, highlighting both areas of potential synergy and opportunities for differentiation.

This systematic mapping revealed several patterns in the current bioeconomy support landscape:

- A predominance of specialized initiatives focusing on specific aspects of bioeconomy (e.g., business models, data, innovation, policy, small-scale activities)
- Varying levels of practical implementation support
- Limited mechanisms for structured knowledge transfer between regions
- Few platforms offering comprehensive support across different regional maturity levels
- Few online hubs that facilitate networking, knowledge exchange, and collaboration

These findings directly informed the development of the BIO2REG network concept, particularly its emphasis on providing integrated support for practical implementation, facilitating structured cross-regional learning, and accommodating regions at different stages of bioeconomy development.

2.2 Initial Concept Development

Based on the insights gained from the mapping exercise, an initial concept for the BIO2REG network was developed by KVC in close collaboration with BIOCOM and FZJ. This concept was designed to:

- Address identified gaps in the current landscape of bioeconomy support
- Complement rather than duplicate existing initiatives
- Leverage synergies with related projects
- Provide distinctive value through unique services and approaches

The initial concept outlined the network's objectives, target audience, core services, operational structure, and differentiation strategy. Particular attention was given to how BIO2REG could build upon and extend valuable work from existing or completed projects, ensuring continuity and adding new dimensions to available resources.

2.3 Dual Validation Process

To ensure the BIO2REG network concept effectively addresses real needs and provides meaningful value, a two-pronged validation approach was designed.

2.3.1 Validation with the Advisory Board

The initial validation of the BIO2REG network concept was conducted through consultation with the project's Advisory Board. This expert consultative body reviewed a comprehensive document outlining the network concept, its proposed services, and differentiation strategy within the European bioeconomy landscape. The Advisory Board, comprising of specialists from various domains of bioeconomy and regional development, provided expert feedback on the concept's viability, potential impact, and alignment with regional needs (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Advisory Board key recommendations

- Provide certificates for training offered / LinkedIn badges
- Adopt a supportive, user-oriented approach for compilation tools, ensuring repository accessibility and practical relevance
- Include maturity level filters in the resources repository
- Integrate a complementary survey in the matchmaking event process to gather additional information beyond the baseline questionnaire (referenced in Deliverable 6.4)

This strategic consultation helped identify potential blind spots, refine the service offerings, and strengthen the network's value proposition before wider implementation. The Advisory Board's feedback was particularly valuable in assessing how effectively BIO2REG complements existing bioeconomy networks while addressing identified gaps. Their insights helped ensure that the BIO2REG network concept is robust, relevant, and strategically positioned to meet its objectives of supporting regional bioeconomy transition in a way that builds upon rather than duplicates existing initiatives.

2.3.2 Validation of the Network Concept in Regional Network Events

The second validation pathway involved direct engagement with potential users through dedicated regional events organized in five European countries: Spain, Greece, Czech Republic, Germany, and Sweden (T2.3 according to the D.O.A). These Regional Network Events brought together diverse stakeholders from the bioeconomy landscape in each host country. A dedicated session specifically addressed the validation of BIO2REG network concept.

Participants were introduced to the proposed BIO2REG network structure, services, and differentiation approach. Following the presentation, attendees engaged in a structured feedback session using a predefined set of questions designed to assess the concept's relevance, usability, and potential value for their regional context.

This direct validation with potential users across different European regions provided insights into regional priorities, preferences, and needs. The geographic diversity of the events ensured the network concept was tested against varying bioeconomy maturity levels, regional priorities, and cultural contexts. Figure 3 below summarizes the key feedback received from surveyed stakeholders.

Figure 3. Key feedback received

Most valued services and functionalities

- Differences were found between regions
- Resources and tools repository, Training activities, Community & Networking space, and Events were well valued in all countries

Additional functionalities or suggested

- Matchmaking tools and events
- Company visits, excursions, and hands-on best-practice examples
- Regional funding opportunities / alerts
- Published bioeconomy articles section
- Opportunity for Public Contributions
- Newsletters
- AI-powered bioeconomy updates

- Research participation expressions of interest
- Competitions and challenges
- Support for connecting bioeconomy innovations with SMEs
- Formats for learning from failure (e.g. "Fuckup-Nights")
- Innovation support through concrete use-case-based networking
- Localised support
- Multilingual access
- Collaborative tools
- Targeted resources for students, SMEs, and early-stage project

Most valuable topics for webinars on regional bioeconomy transition

- Differences were found between regions
- The majority of respondents in all countries showed interest in:
 - Funding opportunities for bioeconomy projects,
 - Best practices and success stories
 - Value chain development and stakeholder engagement
- Policy frameworks for regional bioeconomy and Technological innovations in bioeconomy were also found valuable by a portion of respondents.
- Other specific topics mentioned: social promotion, citizen science, social Scoring for engagement and visibility

Following the collection of feedback, the project team held dedicated internal meetings to analyse all input received, prioritized suggestions based on feasibility, resource availability, and alignment with project objectives, and made collective decisions regarding their implementation timeline. KVC, as the responsible partner for the development of the network, with the collaboration of BIOCOM, which is responsible for the development of the online hub, has already implemented the most feasible changes to the network design and functionality in this final concept version. Other suggestions are being evaluated for potential future implementation as the network evolves, while additional feedback will be considered when designing specific activities in the coming months and when selecting tools, resources, best practices, and other content for the network repository. While some suggestions will not be implemented due to resource constraints, this collaborative approach ensured that stakeholder input is meaningfully incorporated into the current conceptual framework and will continue to guide both near-term and long-term network development activities.

3 BIO2REG Network Overview

3.1 Vision and Mission

The BIO2REG network aims to promote the development of systemic and circular bioeconomy transitions across various regions in Europe. This network will be a central hub integrated into the project's website, serving as both a resource repository and a dynamic space for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and stakeholder interaction. The primary goal is to foster regional bioeconomy cooperation by connecting regional stakeholders and supporting them in their activities to engage people, promote innovation, and facilitate the sharing of best practices.

3.2 Objectives

The network is an informal association of actors engaged in the regional bioeconomy transition, aimed at facilitating in-depth exchanges on implementation topics. The focus is on the comprehensive transition of entire regions and the broader bioeconomy system.

The hub will focus on achieving the following objectives:

- Activating regions: Encourage regional engagement in bioeconomy initiatives.
- Connecting people: Foster relationships between regional stakeholders and bioeconomy experts interested in bioeconomy transition of regions.
- Facilitating knowledge exchange: Share challenges, best practices, innovations, and lessons learned in regional bioeconomy transition.
- Providing a regional perspective: Highlight the importance of regionalisation in the bioeconomy and a systemic approach.
- Encouraging collaboration and co-ordination: Build trust and strengthen cooperation across regions.
- Promoting innovation and learning: Facilitate the transfer of knowledge to advance bioeconomy model regions.
- Lobbying and advocacy: Support regional bioeconomy policies and initiatives.

3.3 Target Audience and Stakeholders

The network will be open to everyone upon registration, although it will primarily target:

- Local development agents
- (Regional) public sector representatives
- Regional bioeconomy clusters
- Entrepreneurs
- Company representatives
- Researchers
- Civil society representatives

By joining the network, members will gain access to:

- A wide range of tools and resources
- Networking opportunities with regional stakeholders, other regions, and bioeconomy experts including Matchmaking events
- Priority access to events, training programmes, and other programmes as the BIO2REG exchange instrument
- Knowledge-sharing opportunities: exchange experiences, best practices, and lessons learned
- Regular updates on bioeconomy-related initiatives, projects, and events

4 Network Hub Structure and Services

The network hub will be organised into the following key sections:

- Home/Welcome Page
- Resources and tools repository
- Community and networking space
- Training and mentoring services
- Events
- Contact and support

- Profile

Figure 4. BIO2REG Network hub menu

4.1 Home/Welcome Page

- **Overview of the network and its objectives:** (See Section 2).
- **Latest news and announcements:** News or updates from the network, promoting the features and opportunities.
- **Featured resources and events:** Highlighted links to specific resources we want to feature and have uploaded to the Resources and Tools section.

4.2 Resources and Tools Repository

- **Project-developed resources and tools:** Including the stakeholder guides on transition measures, the MCA stakeholder guides, the database of bioeconomy tools, etc.
- **External resources and materials relevant to regional bioeconomy transition:** Promote additional resources identified from other projects and relevant materials (such as the ones extracted from Deliverable 2.2 Database of user-friendly tools for regional cooperation towards circular and systemic bioeconomy model regions). There will be a form available to all registered members that allows submission of additional resources or tools (See Annex 2). In addition, any consortium member can contribute to this repository by identifying relevant resources using the form to upload new content, which will be reviewed by KVC before publication.

4.3 Community & Networking Space

- **Discussion and networking space:** We will provide a space for members to discuss various topics of interest through a LinkedIn Discussion Group. This group will be public, allowing participants to discover new contacts, connect with them on LinkedIn, and explore potential collaborations. This approach allows us to avoid the responsibility of moderating the discussions and manage personal data while still offering participants the opportunity to engage in conversations—an essential objective of the network. (Responsible: BIOC).
- **Thematic matchmaking events:** Members will be invited to participate in these online meetups focused on specific themes. To that aim, regions will have to answer a survey that includes: key bioeconomy focus areas (forestry, agriculture, blue bioeconomy, etc.), Development stage (beginning, developing, advanced), specific challenges they are facing, areas of expertise/success, specific collaboration interests and resources they can share with other regions. Based on this information the network will organise thematic matchmaking events where regions can establish connections, share their experiences and exchange knowledge, looking for potential matches to discuss collaboration.
- **Success stories and best practices from different regions:** We will create a dedicated space for participants to share their success stories in regional bioeconomy transition. Best practices are considered powerful tools for network members to engage broader audiences—particularly in regions less familiar with the bioeconomy—by demonstrating its development potential in a concrete and relatable way. To populate this section, we can draw on the best practices and success cases compiled in D1.4: Best practice for regional transitions to bioeconomy model regions and other activities such as the Webinars where member will be invited to share their experiences.

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There will be a form available to all registered members that allows submission of additional success stories or best practices (See Annex 2).

4.4 Training and Mentoring Services

Training activities: This section of the network hub will offer training opportunities and specialised programs to support regions in their transition to a bioeconomy. Members will have access to webinars and trainings that introduce key tools, provide a platform for experience-sharing, and facilitate discussions with experts on challenges and emerging concerns. The topics will be tailored to the needs identified in regional and interregional network events, ensuring relevant and practical support for participants.

Exchange instrument: This section will provide network members with access to register and apply for participation in the BIO2REG exchange program. Through this application process, selected regions will receive mentoring services and opportunities for on-site visits to other regions to exchange experiences and observe relevant bioeconomy initiatives.

4.5 Events' Calendar

Calendar of bioeconomy-related events: Any consortium member can contribute to this calendar by identifying relevant events. There will be a form available to all registered members that allows submission of additional events.

4.6 Contact and Support

- FAQs and guidelines for using the network hub
- Contact details of designated partner

4.7 Profile

In this section members will be able to manage their account, including editing their contact information and close their account.

5 Registration Process

To become a member of the network hub, users must complete a registration process.

There are two ways to sign up for the network:

1. Sign on using LinkedIn login.
2. Sign on and create a network-specific login.
This involves filling out a registration form with the commonly required information: name, surname, organisation, country, email, and password.

As part of the registration process, users will also be required to complete the Baseline questionnaire, which captures initial data on their current bioeconomy status and needs (included in Deliverable 6.5 Baseline report) (See Figure 4). Once registered, users will be able to access the network hub by logging in with their email and password, or via LinkedIn login.

Figure 5. Baseline questionnaire

The baseline questionnaire integrated into the network registration process serves a dual purpose in the BIO2REG project's monitoring and evaluation framework. This survey will establish an initial benchmark by:

- Assessing members' awareness and familiarity with the bioeconomy
- Assessing the bioeconomy landscape in members' regions: The questionnaire will capture the current stage of bioeconomy development or development potential in each member's region, providing a comprehensive mapping of starting points across the network.
- Understanding member expectations and needs: By identifying specific requirements, priorities, and expectations from network members at the outset, we can tailor services and resources to better meet their needs.

The data collected through this baseline survey will play a crucial role in measuring the network's effectiveness and impact. By establishing clear starting points for each member and region, the project will be able to conduct a thorough impact assessment at its conclusion, demonstrating the tangible contributions of the BIO2REG network to regional bioeconomy advancement across Europe.

This approach ensures a robust evaluation methodology that can effectively capture both qualitative and quantitative changes resulting from network participation over time.

6 Synergies with Existing Networks and Initiatives

As stated in the introduction, the BIO2REG Network has been designed with a clear awareness of the existing European bioeconomy initiatives ecosystem. Our value proposition lies not in competing with these initiatives, but in establishing strategic synergies that enhance the collective impact of the European movement towards a sustainable, circular and systemic bioeconomy. Below, we present our synergy strategy that seeks to maximise collaboration and minimise duplication of efforts.

Complementing and updating of training resources

The BIO2REG network plans to take a strategic approach to training that builds upon existing resources rather than creating everything from scratch.

Specifically:

- A. BIO2REG will leverage training materials already developed by initiatives like BioRural and MainstreamBio
- B. Rather than duplicating efforts, BIO2REG will:
 - Complement existing training where gaps exist
 - Update outdated content to ensure it remains relevant
 - Customize training based on specific regional needs
- C. The approach will be needs-driven, using feedback from regional and interregional network events to identify:
 - What gaps need addressing
 - What specific regional requirements need custom solutions

- D. This represents an efficient use of resources and knowledge by building upon foundations that already exist

Compilation of knowledge, tools, cases of success and best practices

BIO2REG network will conduct a systematic compilation of tools, best practices and success cases documented by previous and ongoing initiatives, creating a centralised repository that synthesises the most relevant and applicable knowledge. This repository will feature user-friendly filters designed to help users—regardless of their level of expertise or stage of bioeconomy development—easily identify the tools that best suit their needs.

Collaborative dissemination platform

Other initiatives will be invited to present their developed tools in our network, enhancing their dissemination and exploitation through:

- Joint tool demonstration webinars
- Featured presentations at network events
- Dedicated spaces in our resource repository
- Coordinated communication campaigns

The BIO2REG Network's synergy strategy is designed to create a collaborative ecosystem where each initiative can maintain its unique identity and focus, whilst benefiting from a shared infrastructure of knowledge, resources and relationships. Through this integrated approach, we aim to accelerate the transition towards prosperous and sustainable regional bioeconomy across Europe, maximising the collective impact of the various ongoing efforts and avoiding fragmentation of the bioeconomy support landscape.

7 Dissemination Strategy

The BIO2REG network will employ a multi-channel dissemination strategy to ensure maximum visibility and engagement across diverse European bioeconomy stakeholders. Our approach combines targeted in-person events, digital communication channels, and strategic outreach activities to build a robust and engaged network membership.

Regional network events

A cornerstone of our dissemination strategy will be a series of regional events hosted across five European countries: Czech Republic, Greece, Germany, Spain and Sweden. These events will serve as official platforms to introduce the network concept, showcase its benefits, and articulate its value proposition to potential members.

During these events, we will:

- Collect contact information from interested parties
- Conduct brief surveys to understand specific needs and expectations
- Create a database of potential members who will receive formal invitations to join once the network is officially launched

Digital communication channels

The BIO2REG network will leverage existing project communication infrastructure, including:

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- **Project Website:** A dedicated section will be developed on the project website, featuring detailed information about the network, its benefits, and joining procedures.
- **Social Media Campaigns:** Targeted campaigns will be deployed across LinkedIn, Twitter, and other relevant platforms using visually engaging content and dedicated hashtags.
- **Special Launch Newsletter:** A special edition newsletter will be created specifically for the network launch, highlighting its features, benefits, and how to join.

Partner-Led Institutional Dissemination

Each project partner will take an active role in network dissemination by leveraging their established institutional communication channels to reach their existing networks:

- Institutional websites featuring announcements about the BIO2REG Network
- Organisational social media accounts to share network updates and benefits
- Institutional newsletters sent to their established contact databases
- Direct communication with their existing stakeholder networks and contacts
- Proactive identification and outreach to potential users within their regions and sectors

8 Next steps

The BIO2REG network is planned to be launched in summer 2025. In the coming months leading up to the launch, several key activities will be undertaken to ensure a successful network deployment.

A dissemination campaign will be conducted to invite stakeholders across European regions to join the network. This outreach effort will target participants from the regional stakeholder events, and identified stakeholder groups, leveraging existing project partnerships to build initial network membership.

Content development will be an ongoing priority, with resources, tools, and best practices being continuously uploaded to the various network sections. To ensure systematic and collaborative content curation, an internal work division document is being prepared to assign responsibilities for event organization and content provision across different network sections among project partners.

In addition, the project team will organize and conduct two interregional network events to further engage potential members and demonstrate the network's value proposition. These events will serve to train and mentor regions in the network and accompany their transition towards bioeconomy model regions, considering region-specific conditions and challenges.

This coordinated approach will ensure that when the network launches in summer 2025, it will offer substantial value to its members from day one, with a robust content repository, active community spaces, and a calendar of engaging activities already in place.

Annex 1. Bioeconomy Initiatives Mapping

Project Name	Services	Website	Status	Online network hub
BE-Rural	Initiative establishing Open Innovation Platforms in five Eastern European countries; Assesses regional biomass potential; Engages citizens through interactive formats; Develops regional bioeconomy strategies with local stakeholders; Builds on previous H2020 project experiences; No online network hub	https://be-rural.eu/	Completed - Operational	No
BIOEAST Initiative	Macro-regional initiative focused on developing cross-sectorial bioeconomy strategies for Central and Eastern Europe; Establishes multi-stakeholder networks; Identifies common research challenges; Provides evidence-based policy support; Improves skills through training; Develops funding synergies; Increases visibility of regional bioeconomy potential; No online network hub	https://bioeast.eu/	Renewed / New Phase	No
BIOinSouth	Multi-actor regional groups (MARGs) involving quadruple helix stakeholders; Regional HUBs in eight Southern European regions; Integrated toolkit for environmental impact assessment; Regional monitoring system for bioeconomy sectors; Policy recommendations for sustainability in industrial bio-based systems	https://bioinsouth.eu/	Starting	No
BIOMODELS4REGIONS	Initiative supporting innovative regional governance models for better-informed decision-making; Builds on bioeconomy clusters and previous best practices; Demonstrates results in 6 pilot regions	https://biomodel4regions.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	Yes

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Project Name	Services	Website	Status	Online network hub
BioMonitor	Bioeconomy monitoring and data collection initiative; Data-sharing platform for bioeconomy indicators; Community of statistical experts and policymakers; No online network hub	https://biomonitor.eu/	Completed - Operational	No
BioRegio	Initiative promoting circular economy of biological streams; Focuses on improving knowledge, increasing recycling rates and sharing expertise; Activities include policy development, best practices identification and stakeholder meetings; No online network hub	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/bio-regio/	Completed - Operational	No
Bioregions Facility	Collaborative initiative for regional forest-based bioeconomy development; Support for policy learning through webinars and study tours; Catalysation of bioeconomy business through matchmaking and strategic partnerships; Activities to improve understanding of bioeconomy and strengthen societal engagement	https://bioregions.efi.int/	Established /Mature	No
BioRural	Initiative centred on three pillars (Knowledge, Network, Business Models) feeding into a publicly available BioRural Toolkit; Includes information gap analysis and knowledge exchange; Establishes 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms; Collects circular success stories; Develops business model blueprints; Offers capacity building through regional workshops	https://biorural.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	Yes
BIOTRANSFORM	Framework and knowledge base for policymakers; Focus on accelerating transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular bio-based systems; Development of tools for setting informed priorities aligned with environmental, economic and social goals; Support for policy decisions that align with supply-and-demand trends in related industries and value chains; No online network hub	https://www.biotransform-project.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	No

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Project Name	Services	Website	Status	Online network hub
BioVoices	Initiative to increase quality, relevance and social acceptability of bio-based products; Creates a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) platform; Develops stakeholder-oriented actionable knowledge; Raises citizen awareness; Supports co-creation among quadruple helix stakeholders (civil society/users, industry, researchers, public authorities)	https://biovoices.eu/	Completed - Operational	No
CEE2ACT	Initiative supporting national bioeconomy strategies in 10 Central and Eastern European countries; Establishing National Bioeconomy Hubs; Facilitating knowledge exchange; Building stakeholder capacities; Providing digital solutions for green transition; No online network hub	https://www.cee2act.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	No
European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet)	Alliance of 160 EU-funded projects and initiatives focused on bioeconomy promotion; Maximises knowledge sharing, networking and coordination of joint activities; Increases awareness of sustainable circular bioeconomy; Stimulates debate and mutual learning; Identifies impact-oriented strategies; Facilitates stakeholder networking; Works in close collaboration with European Commission and CBE JU; No online network hub	https://eubionet.eu/	Established/ Mature	No
MainstreamBio	Initiative offering catalogues of small-scale bio-based technologies and business models; Best practices for nutrient recycling; Decision Support System for biomass utilization; Bioeconomy Repository with educational materials; BioForum for stakeholder exchange; Guidance on sustainability schemes	https://mainstreambio-project.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	Yes

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Project Name	Services	Website	Status	Online network hub
POWER4BIO	Initiative to increase capacity of regional and local policy makers to structure their bioeconomy; Focuses on knowledge and best practice exchange within and among regions; Fosters mutual learning and collaboration among regional stakeholders; Supports development of sustainable bioeconomy value chains within 10 participant regions (including 5 from Central and Eastern Europe) from 9 countries; No online network hub	https://power4bio.eu/	Completed - Operational	No
ROBIN	Initiative focused on bioeconomy governance practices; Enhancing understanding of bioeconomy benefits among all stakeholders; Improving regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement; Supporting better informed bioeconomy strategies for investment in sustainable business opportunities; Working to improve environmental footprint of bio-based products; Increasing cross-regional coordination under the CCRI to address Sustainable Development Goals; No online network hub	https://robin-project.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	No
RuralBioUp	Initiative supporting innovators to scale-up inclusive and small-scale biobased solutions in rural areas; Establishment of 9 regional hubs (multi-actor centres) in 6 EU countries; Implementation of 9 Action Plans on 18 value chains; Support for at least 1,000 innovators; No online network hub	https://www.ruralbioup.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	No
ScaleUp	Initiative to help regional actors overcome bottlenecks towards fully exploiting bioeconomy potentials; Focus on increasing capacity of multi-actor partnerships to accelerate marketable bio-based solutions; Improving knowledge about nutrient recycling potential; Deploying existing practical and scientific knowledge; Raising	https://www.scaleup-bioeconomy.eu/es/inicio/	In progress/ Ongoing	No

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Project Name	Services	Website	Status	Online network hub
	awareness of bioeconomy potential among local communities; Strengthening collaboration between stakeholders; Promoting regional transitions towards sustainable, regenerative, inclusive and just circular bioeconomy; No online network hub			
ShapingBio	Initiative to improve information basis about bioeconomy activities and best practices; Focus on enabling cross-sectoral and cross-governmental exchange; Aims to provide better understanding of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem; Working to reduce fragmentation in the bioeconomy landscape; Contributing to better governance and improved exploitation of bioeconomy potential; No online network hub	https://www.shapingbio.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	No
SUSTRACK	Supports policymakers in developing sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular biobased systems; Provides knowledge and tools for monitoring and assessing environmental, social and economic impacts; Focuses on identifying priorities and defining actions to support policy makers; Considers EU, regional and cross-territorial value chains in promoting sustainable transition; No online network hub	https://sustrack.eu/	In progress/ Ongoing	No
Transition2Bio	Initiative focused on communication, education and stakeholder engagement for bioeconomy; Awareness raising and education activities; Community building across diverse stakeholder groups; No online network hub	https://www.transition2bio.e u	Completed - Operational	No

Annex 2. Network Forms by Section

Form to add external resources and tools:

Form fields:

- *Tool Name
- *Type (multiple-choice)
- *Maturity Level
- *Short Description – Brief summary of the tool and its purpose.
- Organisation Name – The name of the entity responsible for the tool.
- Links – Links to tool website or key documents
- Contact information

(*) Required

Search options: Type (Filter), Area of application (Filter), key words

1. Type:

- Guides and methodologies
- Models and simulations
- Databases and digital platforms
- Indicators and metrics
- Financing tools
- Training and capacity-building programs
- Case studies and best practices
- Social engagement
- Other

2. Maturity level

- Emerging
- Developing
- Mature

Form to add success stories and best practices:

Form fields:

- *Title – A brief and descriptive title for the success story.
- *Organisation Name – The name of the entity responsible for the initiative.
- *Country – Possibility to include more than one (Multiple choice - dropdown menu, including others (specify))
- Region – Possibility to include more than one (open ended)
- *Sector – The specific industry or field (e.g., agriculture, forestry, biotechnology). (Multiple choice - dropdown menu, including others (specify))
- *Short Description – A summary of the case (max. 300 words).
- Key Activities – A brief description of the actions implemented.
- Results & Impact – The outcomes achieved, including qualitative and quantitative impacts. (optional)
- *Links – Links to initiative website or key documents
- Photos

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- Contact Information – Details of a contact person for further inquiries (Name and email).

(*) Required

Search options: Country/(Filter), Sector (Filter),

Form to add events:

Form fields:

- *Event name
- *Event type (multiple-choice: Conference, Workshop, Webinar, Training, Networking Event, Exhibition, Policy Meeting, Other (specify))
- *Date and time
- *Event format (Online, in-person or blended)
- [if event format in-person or blended are selected] *Location
- *Short Description
- *Link – Link for more information
- Contact Information – Details of a contact person for further inquiries.

(*) Required